

Efficacy of Social Studies Curriculum in Promoting Entrepreneurial Skills among Colleges of Education Students in North-Central, Nigeria

Muhammad, Nasa¹
muhdnasai@gmail.com,
07036167422

Ismail, Musa²
musaismail002@gamil.com
07069099930

¹Department of Arts and Social Science Education, Faculty of Education,
Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria

²Examination Department, National Teachers' Institutes, (NTI), Kaduna Nigeria

Abstract

This study investigated the efficacy of Social Studies curriculum in promoting entrepreneurial skills among students in colleges of education in North-Central Nigeria. The study was guided by one research objective, one corresponding research question and one hypothesis. Descriptive survey method research design was adopted. The population of the study consisted of 6,836 students during the 2022/2023 academic session in the colleges of education. A sample of 400 students was drawn from the population using multi-stage sampling technique, that is, purposive sampling was adopted in selecting the colleges, proportionate sampling was adopted to determine samples from the selected colleges and simple random sampling was used to select the respondents from each sampled college. The sample size was determined by Research Advisors (2010) table of determining sample size. The data used in the study was collected through researcher-made questionnaire vetted by a team of experts in Statistics and Language departments. Data collected was analysed using mean, standard deviation, and Chi-square test of independence. The hypothesis was retained because no significant relationship was found. The findings thus indicate that specific aspects of the curriculum, such as exposure to innovative ideas and economic activities, significantly influence students' interest in entrepreneurship. While the study supports the hypothesis of no significant difference in students' opinions on the curriculum's impact, recommendations are made to enhance the curriculum by incorporating practical experiences and expanding entrepreneurship education components.

Keywords: Social Studies, Teaching methods, Employment and Entrepreneur

Introduction

Functional educational development is apparently the most important ingredient that guarantees every country's development in all ramifications, because education is the key for sustainable development. This aphorism "education is not an end, itself, but, a means to an end" further buttresses the undeniable role of education towards the development of every nation. However, Social Studies as a distinctive Subject which plays a balancing role in solving the problems of every society, Nigeria inclusive, it is of paramount importance to canvass for a qualitative education. In view of the above, Udoh, Nsit and Ukpong (2014) reaffirmed that education has often been described as a powerful instrument of liberation from disease, ignorance and poverty. It is presumably established fact that, Social Studies curriculum is a well sought out from the needs, desires and aspirations of the society.

This is owing to the fact that the subject is dynamic in nature which fits in to the dynamism of the ever-changing world we live. According to Sofadekan (2012), before the introduction of western education in Nigeria, there had been a traditional form of education which was not rigidly structured. The purpose of traditional education was clear because functionalism was the main guiding principle that is, the curriculum was relevant to the needs of the society. Traditional education was generally a means for immediate induction into society and a preparation for adulthood. Abdul-Kabir (2014) observed that Social Studies education is a subject that develops in learners the right type of values and attitudes that are needed to create a peaceful and sustainable society. Social Studies education teaches

values that would enable peaceful social Integration in Students. Values like maintenance of discipline, respect for law and order, recognition of the principles of cultural relativity and the effect of cultural ethnocentrism, respect for other people's rights, formation of social competency, and citizenship education (Adesina & Odedeji, 2011).

However, Nwaoga and Omeke (2012) established that, skills shortage, as earlier mentioned, remains a serious constraint in Nigeria. Over 80% of graduates in Nigeria are unemployed, yet they have the qualifications, Unemployment in Nigeria appears to be a labour market paradox, and can be attributed to prevailing skills deficit and skills mismatch. Most of the employers, therefore, select fresh graduates who studied in the relevant fields for their jobs as trainees for a number of years before decision is taken either to hire them on full-time basis or as casual workers (Kareem, Ademoyewa, Jolaosho, Ojenike & Sodiq, 2015). In this regard, Akiri, Onoja and Kunanzang (2016) buttressed that, the prosperity and progress of a nation depends on the quality of its people. If they are enterprising, ambitious and courageous enough to bear the risk, the community/society will develop quickly. Such people are identified as entrepreneurs and their character reflects entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is no monopoly of any religion or community. Akiri, Onoja and Kunanzang (2016) further opined that, entrepreneurial potential can be found and developed anywhere irrespective of age, qualification, experience or socio-economic background, only efforts are required in the right direction. Social Studies NCE curriculum contents is designed to include aspect that deals with man and his economic activities which exposes the students to activities that will ignites their zeal of becoming conscious of their inherited socioeconomic activities (Haruna & Hassan, 2019). As part of effort to impact entrepreneurship education students in all the colleges of education in Nigeria must undergo a course “entrepreneurship education” as a general course. In order to tackle the problem of unemployment various administrations had expedited the formation of laudable programmes or policies to condense the risk of the scourge such as N-POWER which started in 2016 by President Muhammadu Buhari administration in Batches and has six categories; N-Teach, N-Health, N-Agro, N-Build, N-Creative, and N-Tech respectively. It is against this backdrop this research was conducted.

Meanwhile, no society can grow above the quality of its education. Education has no specific definition in the field of humanity. Let’s examine some scholarly definitions of education. Etymologically, the word “education” is a derivative of the Latin verb “*educare*” meaning ‘to bring up’, ‘to lead out’, ‘to raise up’, ‘to inform’, ‘to teach’ and ‘to train’. In its original sense, to educate means acting in order to lead out fully all the potentialities of an individual. Education is therefore a process of learning, acquiring and transferring knowledge, training, skills, and ideas. Fafunwa, defines it as the “aggregate of all the process by which a child or adult develops the abilities, attitudes and other forms of behavior which are of positive value to the society in which he lives, that is to say, it is a process of disseminating knowledge either to ensure social control or to guarantee rational direction of the society or both” (Nnaemeka, 2011, p.2). Adeel (2010) defines education as a means of transmitting worthwhile ideas that are considered necessary for an individual to conveniently adjust to his total environment. Education is a process that helps an individual to develop his/her whole being, physically. It is a process of transmitting culture in terms of continuity and growth and for disseminating knowledge to ensure social control of individuals (Mvendaga, Ifeanyichukwu & Apine 2014). This has a great implication for Social Studies.

Thus, Zakari (2014) posited that Social Studies is an organized, integrated study of man and his environment. Social Studies as the booster rocket of the human’s development of all the faculties of a child. That will make him an effective citizen. Social Studies aims at offering a comprehensive study which takes care of the Child's cognitive effective and psychomotor domains. Similarly, Adeyemi (2013) Defined Social Studies as a course of discipline gained it is entrance in Nigeria school curriculum shortly after its independence precisely 1963 is at its infancy. Mores so, because of the nature of the subject (Social Studies) its definitions are countless that is why Ediyang, Ubi and Adelikwu (2012) asserted that Social Studies is aimed at inculcating the necessary skills, competences, and intellectual capabilities the learners will use for a healthy living in the society. To further, buttress the importance attached to Social Studies Basiru (2013) posited that, Social Studies presents the dynamics of values, interest and attitudes. Such that will help the leaners in decision making on matters affecting them. Thus, Social Studies is a discipline that equips the leaners with the tools necessary for their survival in the society. In view of this, Social Studies has been presumed as a problem-solving discipline that is capable of fixing socio-political worlds inflicted on the country by number of factors then, and now. In other words, Akinlola (2014) defined Social Studies as the planned and unplanned process by which

individuals acquires values, skills and knowledge which will make them useful to themselves and the society at large. The goals of Social Studies are so beautifully designed to be in line with those of the national goals. Olawumi, Adu, and Adu (2021) reported that, one of the main functions of Social Studies is that it aims to educate learners to live a responsible life now and in the future in their communities. The essence and purpose of establishing the subject varies from one society to another. However, Social Studies curriculum addresses economic, political, psychological, physical and technological relevance of cultural and moral way of life of a people to national development. Its content is organized around social and environmental issues affecting man's existence, ability to perform and conserve the environment for sustainable development (Akpan, 2020). The fundamental focus of Social Studies is man and his complex relationships in the world around and beyond him. The NCE Social Studies curriculum attempts to instill in its products the basic knowledge, desirable values and skills for investigating, analyzing and explaining these interrelationships (NCCE, 2021).

Consequently, the economic entrepreneurship theory was adopted for this study. According to Simpeh (2011), the economic entrepreneurship theory has deep roots in the classical and neoclassical theories of economics, and the Austrian market process (AMP). These theories explore the economic factors that enhance entrepreneurial behavior. Classical Theory; the classical theory extolled the virtues of free trade, specialization, and competition. Neo-classical Theory; the neo-classical model emerged from the criticisms of the classical model and indicated that economic phenomena could be relegated to instances of pure exchange, reflect an optimal ratio, and transpire in an economic system that was basically closed. Austrian Market Process (AMP); these unanswered questions of the neo-classical movement led to a new movement which became known as the Austrian Market process (AMP).

Objective of the Study

Assess the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria

Research Question

To what extent does Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

H₀₁ There is no significant difference in the opinions of students on the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria

Methodology

The descriptive survey method was used for this study. The study covered 12 colleges of education offering Social Studies as a standalone course in North-Central, Nigeria. The population comprises of NCE III students from the colleges of education. The total number of Social Studies Students is 6,836. Research Advisors' (2010) table for determining sample size was the adopted blueprint for selecting number of respondents for the survey. Consequently, a sample size of 400 was adopted for use. The researcher therefore used a structured questionnaire for data collection in the study. The questionnaire was prepared based on four points modified Likert scale in which participants responded to each item with options ranging from Strongly Agreed (S.A) 4, Agreed (A) 3, Disagreed (D) 2 and Strongly Disagreed (SD) 1. Reliability of the instrument was ascertained from a pilot test which was conducted on thirty (30) Social Studies students in Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, Kumbotso, Kano State and the Cronbach's alpha reliability co-efficient index of .827 was obtained. Both descriptive and inferential statistics, such as, mean, standard deviation and Chi-square were used for the data analysis.

Results

Research Question

To what extent does Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria?

To answer this research question, the data collected was subjected to descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. Table 1 presents summary of the result.

Table 1: Summary of Means and Standard Deviations on views of students on the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
1	Skills acquired for Entrepreneurship developments are embedded in NCE curriculum where Man's economic activities are taught as compulsory course.	3.0800	.85465
2	The study of Social Studies at NCE level stimulates self-employment intention where the traditions way of surviving is taught to students.	2.8300	.94251
3	Social Studies curriculum content exposes students to innovative ideas, which does not develop in the students a high level of autonomy.	2.0300	1.13239
4	Social Studies curriculum content does not enhance students' ability of critical and creative thinking.	2.2300	1.13150
5	Social Studies curriculum contents enlightens students on economic activities that existed generations before us, therefore, ignites the zeal to revive them.	2.8775	1.00749
6	Social Studies curriculum does not promote hardworking disposition among students to able to fend for themselves.	2.6300	1.02993
7	Social Studies curriculum does not promote self-awareness and self-confidence among students who use their talents to survive.	2.6500	.98992
8	Social Studies curriculum teaches the students about production system by exploring raw materials within their local community	2.5825	1.13861
9	Entrepreneurship skills taught in Social Studies NCE programme are not practical experiences required for self-employment	2.3900	1.08897
10	Social Studies curriculum contents which target students' manipulative skills such as craft making, drawing, discussion about mineral resources among others stimulate production	2.9525	1.02365
Aggregate Mean		2.62	1.033

Table 1 presents a summary of the means and standard deviations of students' views on the extent to which the Social Studies curriculum for the NCE program promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central Nigeria. This table serves as a crucial component of the study, offering valuable insights into the perceptions of students regarding the integration of entrepreneurship skills within the curriculum. The aggregate mean of 2.62, with a standard deviation of 1.033, indicates that, on average, students held a moderately positive perception of the relationship between the Social Studies curriculum and entrepreneurial skills. This suggests that there is a general inclination among students to view the curriculum positively in terms of fostering entrepreneurial abilities. The standard deviation of 1.033 reflects a moderate level of dispersion in responses, indicating some variability in how students perceive the curriculum's effectiveness in promoting entrepreneurial skills.

Among the individual items listed in Table 1, the highest mean response of 3.08 signifies a strong agreement among students with a particular statement related to the promotion of entrepreneurial skills. This high mean suggests that students are particularly supportive of certain aspects of the curriculum that are perceived to enhance entrepreneurial abilities. Conversely, the lowest mean of 2.03 indicates less agreement with a statement regarding the enhancement of critical and creative thinking skills through the curriculum. This disparity in mean values highlights the varying degrees of support for different aspects of the curriculum in relation to entrepreneurial skills development.

The acceptance of positive response statements and rejection of negative statements by the respondents further underscore the general positive perception of the Social Studies curriculum in fostering entrepreneurial skills. This trend indicates that students are more inclined to acknowledge and appreciate the beneficial aspects of the curriculum that contribute to the development of entrepreneurial competencies.

Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the opinions of students on the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria.

The data collected from students were summarized using tally system based. The summarized data was tested using non-parametric statistical tool of chi-square (χ^2) at 0.05% level of significance. The summary of the hypothesis tested is presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Summary of Chi-square (χ^2) statistics on the opinions of students regarding the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria.

N	χ^2 cal.	Df	α	Sig.	Decision
400	83.069 ^a	9	0.05	0.620	Retained

Source: Field Work

Table 2 shows that the calculated p-value of 0.620 was greater than 0.05 level of significance, while the χ^2 calculated value of 83.069 at df (9). Consequently, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the opinions of students on the extent to which Social Studies curriculum for NCE programme promotes entrepreneurial skills among colleges of education students in North-Central, Nigeria was retained.

Discussion of Findings

The study yielded significant findings that contribute to our understanding of the role of education in fostering entrepreneurship. The analysis of mean, standard deviation, and Chi-square statistics provided valuable insights into students' perceptions and experiences regarding entrepreneurship education. One key finding of the study was the positive perception among students towards Social Studies curriculum's impact on entrepreneurial skills. Students acknowledged the relevance of the Social Studies curriculum in stimulating entrepreneurial thinking and preparing them for economic independence. This finding aligns with previous research (Chineze, Uche & Gabriel 2021) emphasizing the importance of integrating entrepreneurship education within the academic curriculum to cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset. Furthermore, the study highlighted the value of practical experiences in enhancing students' entrepreneurial skills. Students emphasized the importance of hands-on opportunities, such as business idea development and engagement with local businesses, in enriching their understanding of entrepreneurial practices. This finding is consistent with existing literature (Secundo, Mele, Passiante & Albergo) that underscores the significance of experiential learning in entrepreneurship education.

While the study found no significant difference in students' opinions on the promotion of entrepreneurial skills through the curriculum, it identified opportunities for curriculum enhancements to further support entrepreneurial development. Recommendations were made to broaden the curriculum to include entrepreneurship education and practical experiences that guarantee innovative skills among students. This recommendation is supported by previous studies (Lindberg, Bohman, Hulten & Wilson, 2017) advocating for the integration of entrepreneurship modules in educational curricula to foster entrepreneurial competencies. Also, the findings of the study underscore the importance of equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and mindset necessary for entrepreneurial success. By enhancing the Social Studies curriculum to incorporate entrepreneurship education and practical experiences, colleges of education in North-Central Nigeria can better prepare students for the challenges and opportunities of the evolving business landscape. This aligns with the broader goal of education in promoting self-reliance, economic empowerment, and sustainable development.

This study equally found out that Social Studies NCE programme content areas are relevant in promoting determination to focus on innovative skills among students in Colleges of Education, North-Central, Nigeria. This implies that the students perceived that content areas of Social Studies NCE programme acquainted them with determination to focus on innovative skills such as Man's economic activities are taught as compulsory course, Social Studies at NCE level stimulates self-employment intention where the traditions way of surviving are taught to students and Social Studies curriculum content exposes students to innovative ideas, which does not develop in the students a high level of autonomy among others. This means that the content areas of Social Studies NCE programme which

include: Man's economic activities, entrepreneurship education in general studies course and cultural identity and others are capable of making them determined to focus on innovative skills for their survival. This finding was supported by Nuhu, Abdullaheem, Abubakar, Abdurauf and Idiagbo (2021) where they conducted research on "Entrepreneur Skills as Determinants to Job Opportunities among LIS Postgraduate Students in University of Ilorin". They concluded that Entrepreneurial skills equip students with abilities that increase their employment potential and include: the abilities to solve problems, to develop social interaction, abilities to find information and to handle it for decision making, planning, and communication and presentation skills.

Conclusion

The study revealed a generally positive perception among students towards the curriculum's role in fostering entrepreneurial abilities. With an aggregate mean of 2.62 and consistent agreement on key aspects of the curriculum, students demonstrated a recognition of the curriculum's relevance in stimulating self-employment intentions and innovative skills. The findings support the hypothesis of no significant difference in students' opinions on the promotion of entrepreneurial skills through the curriculum, indicating a cohesive viewpoint among students. These results emphasize the importance of the Social Studies curriculum in equipping students with the necessary competencies for entrepreneurial endeavors and self-reliance, suggesting opportunities for curriculum enhancements to further support entrepreneurial development and economic empowerment in the region.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. Colleges of education should consider enhancing the Social Studies curriculum by incorporating practical experiences and real-world applications of entrepreneurial skills. Institutions can better prepare students for self-employment and financial independence by giving them practical opportunity to participate in entrepreneurial activities, such as developing and implementing business ideas. Furthermore, working with nearby companies and entrepreneurs will help students gain insightful knowledge and excellent mentorship, which will enhance their comprehension of entrepreneurial processes.
- ii. Policymakers in the education sector should prioritize the integration of entrepreneurship education within the broader curriculum framework, emphasizing the development of critical and creative thinking skills essential for entrepreneurial success. Advocates for the inclusion of experiential learning opportunities and entrepreneurship modules in the curriculum can help students gain real-world experience and information that is applicable to today's corporate environment. Incentives for collaborations between academic institutions and business partners can also help students receive resources and entrepreneurial know-how.
- iii. Industry leaders and successful entrepreneurs play a crucial role in nurturing the next generation of entrepreneurial talent. Through active participation in mentorship programmes, guest lectures, and internship opportunities, industry leaders can offer invaluable insights and support to students who aspire to pursue entrepreneurial endeavours through active engagement with schools of education. Fostering an innovative, risk-taking, and resilient culture among students can aid in establishing the entrepreneurial attitude required to successfully navigate the obstacles of the corporate world. Furthermore, encouraging programmes that advance entrepreneurship education and skill development will help North-Central Nigeria's entrepreneurial environment become more dynamic and long-lasting.

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